

Title: Comprehensive systematic review of the efficacy, scientific research studies, of Bach Remedies

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The aim of this systematic review is to analyse the randomized control trials conducted in the last decades to prove the efficacy and safety of the Bach Flowers Remedies system (BFRs).

In this study we have undertaken an extensive comprehensive search of the literature using high quality database in the field of biomedical and life sciences literature. To identify the papers, we use a set of keywords and search only studies published in peer review journals using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) review method to examine the studies.

Once the data have been fully extracted and the results completed via statistical analysis, the evaluation of efficacy and safety will be provided. In addition, the review aims to bring clarity and a framework to help future researchers to improve the quality of their study which is often considered a weak point in Complementary Alternative Medicine (CAM) studies.